

VALKYRIES

D7.4 Reference Integration and lessons learned

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1. Executive Summary

This document **D7.4 Reference Integration and lessons learned** describes the effectiveness of the VALKYRIES outcomes according to the validation and evaluation methodology (D7.1) on the SGRUN integration of different technologies with the harmonization goals of the Valkyries project. The Report is addressing the challenges described at T2.1 and includes guidelines, filed notes and lessons learned that may guide further related developments and support normalization actions.

This deliverable includes all the activities related to proactive actions performed in the task T7.3 and the results following the testing of the components, modules, interfaces, procedures, etc., reference integrated as well as their interoperability, normalization, and harmonization to support first aid responses on disaster scenarios. This covers the evaluation of the whole VALKYRIES reference architecture, with integration tests and system validations.

As in the Valkyries methodology several gaps and opportunities were analysed in WP3, 4 and 5, proactive actions were taken in those in order not to have gaps between them. This reflected on the integration decisions on technical issues that were included in the final version of D2.8 (System's Architecture) as well as on procedures to be followed during the test. Such procedures were related either with "on the field" procedures followed by first responders and internal procedures related with the operations of the SGRUN system per se.

Following this, functional, modular, inter-modular, scalability and security tests were executed on the testbed developed and integrated in the adapted virtual labs and testbeds as per T7.1 results. The validation and evaluation of integrations for use case demonstration and their outcomes have been performed, including a broad study based on the expectations and null/alternative hypothesis, and the impact of the massive cross-border demonstrations in both the attending stakeholders and the expected operational and collaborative enhancements. The latter will also assess the effect of the demonstration outcomes bearing in mind the opinions of experts.

The following summarises the main contributions of **D7.4**:

- Harmonisations verified by Inspection, analysis, tests, and demonstration.
- The level of achievements on the scope of the harmonization opportunities and justification.
- The results achieved in each validation test and the quality of the results obtained through **all UCs** testing of the above.
- Evidence of implementation and compliance of the goals against actual performance of the SGRUN system versus the results of traditional Civil Protection systems in place.

This final version of the document compiles the evidence to test the results through UCs on the harmonisation opportunities proposed in VALKYRIES versus SINGRUN system performance.

All changes from the previous version have been highlighted with yellow in the present document.

2. Identification

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3. Purpose and goals of T7.3 and this report

Task 7.3 was designed to follow and report the outcomes of the Valkyries project as integrated against their technical expectations and their performance on specific harmonization goals.

Such integration testing was executed in different stages, following the methodology presented in Paragraph 4 of this document, as verified and validated by inspection and modules testing.

Validation by Inspection is the examination of the product or system using the basic senses, so they are physically examined based on their required physical characteristics and the control mechanisms they are supposed to present. Similarly, in the case of a software system, testers must check that its user interface is as required, presenting all the fields and data entry buttons it is supposed to have, etc.

In the context of VALKYRIES, a thorough documentary inspection of the Project results were carried out throughout its product life cycle, in which the evaluators were able to constantly provide information, assessments and, when required, the approval of the Consortium's decisions. These documentary inspections were complemented by a direct human inspection of the capabilities delivered, mainly targeting user interfaces and related user-friendly information sources.

Regarding the inspection of codes and software, human evaluation measures were supported by third-party instruments deployed in the development environment and on the test beds (Virtual Laboratory, dedicated test tools on blockchain recordings, etc.), which automatically facilitated the discovery of inconsistencies, errors, missing fields, etc.

The results of such testing are presented in ANNEX A whilst the conclusions, lessons learned and recommendations for further developments are presented in the following paragraphs.

The following Table summarizes the Type of testing and their relevance to Valkyries Goals and objectives.

3.1. Requirements compliance matrix

ID	Priority	Traceability with objectives	WBS Deliverables	Compliance	Results
REQ_BASE_T7.3_1	P1	All	D7.4 D7.5 D7.6 D7.7 D7.8	REQUIRED	Achieved. Information available in this document. SIGRUN framework has been used in all UCs
REQ_BASE_T7.3_2	P1	All	D4.2 / D4.6 D5.2 / D5.6 D6.2 / D6.6 D7.4	REQUIRED	Achieved. Gaps were reported in WP3, 4 and 5 as well gaps between the relevant gaps. Proactive actions were taken and integrated in the deliverables of these WPs
REQ_BASE_T7.3_3	P1	VALK-OBJ-3 VALK-OBJ-4 VALK-OBJ-5 VALK-OBJ-6 VALK-OBJ-7 VALK-OBJ-8	D7.4	REQUIRED	Achieved. Information available in this document.
REQ_BASE_T7.3_4	P1	VALK-OBJ-3 VALK-OBJ-4 VALK-OBJ-5 VALK-OBJ-6	D7.4	REQUIRED	Achieved. Information available in this document.

ID	Priority	Traceability with objectives	WBS Deliverables	Compliance	Results
		VALK-OBJ-7 VALK-OBJ-8			
REQ_BASE_T7.3_5	P1	VALK-OBJ-3 VALK-OBJ-4 VALK-OBJ-5 VALK-OBJ-6 VALK-OBJ-7 VALK-OBJ-8	D7.4 D5.4	REQUIRED	Achieved. Information available in this document. Procedures were designed in the document D5.4 - Annex C.
REQ_BASE_T7.3_6	P1	VALK-OBJ-3 VALK-OBJ-4 VALK-OBJ-5 VALK-OBJ-6 VALK-OBJ-7 VALK-OBJ-8	D7.4	REQUIRED	Achieved. Information available in this document.
REQ_BASE_T7.3_7	P1	VALK-OBJ-3 VALK-OBJ-4 VALK-OBJ-5 VALK-OBJ-6 VALK-OBJ-7 VALK-OBJ-8	D7.4	REQUIRED	Achieved. Information available in this document.
REQ_BASE_T7.3_8	P1	VALK-OBJ-3 VALK-OBJ-4 VALK-OBJ-5 VALK-OBJ-6 VALK-OBJ-7 VALK-OBJ-8	D7.4	REQUIRED	Achieved. Information available in this document.
REQ_BASE_T7.3_9	P1	VALK-OBJ-3 VALK-OBJ-4 VALK-OBJ-5 VALK-OBJ-6 VALK-OBJ-7 VALK-OBJ-8	D7.4	REQUIRED	Achieved. Information available in this document.
REQ_BASE_T7.3_10	P1	VALK-OBJ-3 VALK-OBJ-4 VALK-OBJ-5 VALK-OBJ-6 VALK-OBJ-7 VALK-OBJ-8	D7.4	REQUIRED	Achieved. Information available in this document.
REQ_BASE_T7.3_11	P1	VALK-OBJ-3 VALK-OBJ-4 VALK-OBJ-5 VALK-OBJ-6 VALK-OBJ-7 VALK-OBJ-8	D7.4	REQUIRED	Achieved. Testing of blockchain logging SIGRUN module as fully compliant with EU privacy and data acts. Information available in this document.
REQ_BASE_T7.3_12	P1	VALK-OBJ-3 VALK-OBJ-4 VALK-OBJ-5 VALK-OBJ-6 VALK-OBJ-7 VALK-OBJ-8	D7.4 D5.4	REQUIRED	Achieved. Information available in this document. D5.4 - Annex C contents the Risk assessment and Internal security and functionality manual produced and evaluated.
REQ_BASE_T7.3_13	P1	VALK-OBJ-3 VALK-OBJ-4	D7.4	REQUIRED	Achieved. Information available in this document.

ID	Priority	Traceability with objectives	WBS Deliverables	Compliance	Results
		VALK-OBJ-5 VALK-OBJ-6 VALK-OBJ-7 VALK-OBJ-8			

Table 1 – T7.3 Traceability matrix

4. Methodologies on integration and harmonization

In software development, integration testing is essential in ensuring that all system components function correctly and work together seamlessly. Critical bugs can go unnoticed without proper integration testing, leading to significant issues in production environments.

Several computer/software related incidents reported in literature, highlight the importance of integration testing to ensure that all system components work together securely and reliably before deployment to production. The following are the major, as appear also in the relevant literature.

4.1. Integration Testing Techniques

4.1.1. Blackbox Testing

In Integration testing, black box testing checks how well a system works without looking at its internal structure and design. Instead, the tester looks at how it responds to different inputs, like when you press certain buttons or type certain words.

Figure 1 – Black box testing

This Testing ensures the system meets the needs of whoever uses it and finds any mistakes in its design. The test cases come from what the system should do, and then the tester creates scenarios based on that.

A typical example of black box testing is testing a website’s search function. The tester would not examine the code or algorithm used to generate search results. Instead, the tester would input various search queries and analyse the resulting outputs to ensure the search function works as intended.

4.1.2. Whitebox Testing

White Box Testing, referred to as Structural Testing or Clear Box Testing, is a form of software testing that examines the internal functioning of an application. It checks the source code, control flow, and data flow to ensure they all work together correctly. To do this test, you must know what’s happening inside the app and what code was used to make it.

WHITE BOX TESTING

Figure 2 – White box testing

This type of Testing primarily aims to validate the application’s internal logic and ensure that a system works as expected. It’s usually done to ensure the app works correctly when different parts are assembled.

The above two major methodologies may be used in five different integration testing techniques/methodologies.

4.1.3. Types of Integration Testing

The following outlines the five categories of Integration Testing types:

4.1.3.1. Big Bang Testing

Big Bang Testing is a method where all the individual components of a software or a system are integrated and tested at once. Instead of testing each component separately, they’re thrown into the mix to see how they work together. It’s like throwing all the ingredients into a blender and hoping for the best.

The image below shows how to do it. Integrate all the modules from ‘Module 1’ to ‘Module 6’ simultaneously before testing.

Big Bang Integration Testing

Figure 3 – Big Bang Integration testing

Here are some advantages and disadvantages of this Testing:

Advantages:

- Big Bang testing can be done quickly, meaning you can get your product to the market faster.

- It can help identify Big Bang testing can save time and money since all tests can be done simultaneously.
- It provides a good overview of the system's functionality and performance.
- It helps reduce the risk of missing out on any issue during testing problems before the product goes live.

Disadvantages:

- This Testing is challenging to isolate and troubleshoot individual issues.
- It can be costly and time-consuming if there are problems.
- It can be challenging to coordinate with multiple teams and departments or involved agents in real disaster incidents.
- Determining whether the system is ready for launch can be difficult.
- It can be tough to make sure all tests are done correctly.

4.1.3.2. Incremental Testing

It's a software/system development approach that involves testing of small pieces of code as written instead of waiting until the entire program is finished.

The below figure depicts how Integration testing can be divided into Incremental/Non-incremental Testing:

Incremental Testing

Figure 4 – Incremental testing

Advantages:

- Incremental Testing lets you break up the testing process into smaller chunks, so you can get results quicker and find issues faster. This means you can spot problems and figure out how to solve them more quickly.
- Developers can focus on adding features during the testing cycle rather than doing the same tests repeatedly.

- It allows users to test new features or changes to existing features in an isolated environment.
- We ensure the quality of building the application.

Disadvantages:

- This Testing requires a significant amount of planning and coordination.
- It may require additional resources to be available for the testing cycle.
- This Testing is not suitable for large projects that require extensive Testing.
- It can be challenging to identify and fix defects on time.

4.1.4. Stubs and Drivers

First, a stub is a small piece of code that mimics the behaviour of a larger component. It's essentially a stand-in for the real thing, allowing us to test other parts of our code that depend on that component.

Drivers are used in integration testing and can be considered a "placeholder" for system parts that are not yet developed. They simulate the behaviour of the missing components so that other system parts can be tested. Usually, simulators are used to provide the expected outcomes.

Stubs test individual parts of a program or system from the top down, while Drivers allow Testing from the bottom up.

Below is the figure for Stubs and Drivers:

Figure 5 – Stubs and drivers

Advantages of Stubs and Drivers

- Stubs and drivers help to test individual components in isolation from the rest of the system.
- They provide a way to test code before integrating it with other modules.
- They help to reduce the time taken for development by simulating the behavior of other components.
- Help to reduce the risk of bugs caused by integration issues.
- They can test the system before it is ready for integration.

Disadvantages of Stubs and Drivers

- Stubs and drivers can be challenging to create, maintain and debug.
- They can be time-consuming to develop and maintain.
- Stubs and drivers can introduce their bugs into the system.
- They can be challenging to update or modify if the system changes.
- It may not be able to simulate the behaviour of other components accurately.

4.1.5. Bottom-up Integration Testing

Bottom-up integration testing is where we start by testing the most minor components of our software first and then work our way up to the larger ones. It's like building a house from the bottom up – we start with the foundation, then the walls, and finally the roof.

This means that with this integration testing methods, you create a test environment that simulates a user trying to log in, and you would make sure the login works as intended. Once you're confident that the login feature is working correctly, you will test the messaging feature, and it goes on.

Below is the figure of the Bottom-Up Approach:

Figure 6 – Bottom-up integration testing

Advantages

- It is cost-effective and easy to implement.
- It helps spot problems early on in the making process.
- Since tests are done at the component level, it is easier to identify and debug problems.
- It gives an excellent way to check if different parts are working together correctly.

Disadvantages

- It takes a lot of time because you must test each part individually.
- This Testing can be tough to figure out where the issue comes from when different parts are combined.
- It requires significant resources to manage and maintain.
- Maintaining test cases and data for all components can be difficult.

4.1.6. Top-down Integration Testing

Top-down integration testing is when you test the software application or a system from the top (i.e. the user interface) down to the lower levels (i.e. the individual functions and modules).

Top-down integration testing would involve testing the homepage and ensuring it works properly before testing the individual pages. Once you've confirmed that the homepage and individual pages are working together correctly, you can test the components within each page, like the navigation bar and images.

Below is the figure of the Top-down Approach:

Figure 7 – Top-down integration testing

Advantages

- This testing approach allows testers to identify the issues early in the development cycle and fix them accordingly.
- It helps to detect any integration issues between the modules.
- This method is cost-effective as it helps detect problems early in development.

Disadvantages

- It can be time-consuming and costly due to the system's complexity.
- Testing all the scenarios may not be possible due to the system's complexity.
- Determining what's wrong can be tricky if many parts are involved.

4.1.7. Sandwich Testing

Essentially, it's a type of testing where you're testing the middle layer of your application, hence the sandwich analogy. This middle layer is where all the different modules of your application come together and communicate with each other.

So, how do you test this middle layer? Well, that's where integration testing comes in.

By testing software or system using this methodology, it can ensure that all the different layers of code, modules, attached systems, etc. are working together correctly. For example, you might use sandwich testing to test how your software interacts with a database or handles user input. This type of testing is also called Hybrid Integration Testing.

Below is the figure for Sandwich Testing:

Sandwich Testing

Figure 8 – Sandwich testing

Advantages

- Allows for efficient Testing of two unrelated interfaces or components, saving time and resources.
- Can detect bugs.
- Easy to set up and execute.
- It can be used to test different layers of an application or a system.
- Easier to debug since the bug is easily identifiable, and the system is unaffected by other components.

Disadvantages

- Complex setup and configuration required.
- It can be challenging to track down bugs if the test fails.
- Time and resources may be wasted if the tests are poorly planned and executed.
- It may not be able to test all layers in an application adequately.
- It can be questioned to maintain and update tests.

4.2. Integration test strategy in the case of SIGRUN

SIGRUN, the result of the Valkyries project, consists of two different types of components:

- New designed modules acting as the “core” of a system used by Civil Protection authorities in multi-victims’ cross border incidents
- A number of existing systems acting as trusted federated components attached through APIs to the SIGRUN platform, exchanging information one to each other through SIGRUN

As the later are mature well tested systems by their developers, the main effort in integration testing in a system such as SIGRUN is towards integration testing of new components developed and how such imply with the harmonization goals of the project. Such “harmonization” reflects to a complex set of goals and criteria/KPIs that are expected to be verified and endorsed by real users during the UCs as per their expectations.

Based on the above, the integration testing methodology that fits best to the nature of the Valkyries project was decided to follow an **incremental testing approach following the “sandwich” testing methodology**.

Integration testing design followed the above methodology in different stages of SIGRUN development. In these cases, different modules of the SIGRUN system were tested incrementally, as reported in the ANNEX A of the present document.

4.3. Harmonization through integration

Valkyries harmonisation framework is based in OODA cycle detailed in document D2.5 Harmonisation framework.

During such OODA execution throw-out WPs 2, 3, 4 and 5, it was realized that an integrated process and application landscape that is flexible and efficient is needed in today’s Civil Protection systems. It lays the foundation for ongoing growth strategies, greater first responders’ performance reaching a faster response to new risks, and quicker supply chains/logistics support to first responders less complex.

Heterogeneous process models organizational structures/roles and diverse IT landscapes in use, cause significant inefficiencies for operational processes and communication between different Civil Protection systems in place. That is why most industries are investing heavily in the establishment of globally harmonized processes that focus on business improvements.

Civil Protection systems in EU can be viewed or considered as an ISO-OSI model consisting of the following layers:

Figure 9 – Layers in Civil Protection

- The **Physical layer** is always different and there is no way to consider any harmonisations or integrated systems performing with no such reality in mind. Geographical factors and human constructions are not following any specific standards or pattern, causing huge problems harmonizing all the layers above.
- **Risks on the physical layer** are always different and dynamic. As so, any attempt to classify them into predefined patterns is risky as, in real, they may cause different effects in different locations or areas than the ones expected.

- Based on recognized risks, Civil Protection Authorities and related Agencies prepare different **blueprints** on scenarios of future catastrophic incidents.
- The expected performance of involved Agencies in catastrophic events as per the expectations of such scenarios' design reflects on their **organizational structure**. This is difficult or impossible to harmonize due to the restrictions of the layers bellow and the origin of the Agencies. Some come with a military background whilst others follow civil or volunteer's management.
- The **communication** layer of the above model depends today only on the availability of terrestrial communication networks deployed in advanced countries, such in most areas in EU. Such communications are crucial of different Agencies or Authorities to communicate to each other or to their first responders acting on the field. Even though the communication technologies are today well standardized and easy to access, still this layer suffers from the lack of terrestrial communications (due to catastrophes in infrastructure or no communication coverage in remote areas) and the vast use of analog voice-based channels, still dominating the common practice of most First Responders' organizations.
- **Command and Controls** in the above model are multi-layered. Typically, they are deployed near the incidents or on a peripheral level, whilst is huge catastrophic multi victims' incidents C2s of Civil Protection Authorities need to be involved and engage. This requirement is also a must in the case in cross-border incidents of any size, as several bilateral agreements between countries may filter the information exchanges beyond the borders.
- The **application tools and equipment** available to first responders is vital for the correct operation of all the bellow layers. As so, technologies available are always try to provide their most in order the 4 levels bellow them to be able to perform.

The interoperability between different Agencies in the same country or between different countries in cross-border events, needs to maximize the homogeneous performance of different layers, as the above, sharing information as needed with precise, secure and not delayed manner as in the following schema.

Figure 10 – Interoperability between agencies

Following this result, integration tests were designed accordingly.

5. Proactiveness during the Valkyries/SIGRUN design

In the Valkyries project, the above were implemented towards the testing of the SIGRUN system as an integrated technological platform in two stages:

- An early, proactive stage during the analysis of systems-as-is and gaps and opportunities versus the designs of the SIGRUN architecture. In all cases, the effort was to minimize future gaps that would appear during the UCs testing as problems or system failures. Such efforts, as part of the T7.3, were reported and taken into consideration through the execution of WP3, 4 and 5 as well as during the design of the SIGRUN architecture as appearing in D2.8 Architecture Design.
- As a set of internal procedures applying on the SIGRUN system, designed to assure the correct and secure handling of different federated systems and data exchanges against recognized risks (cybersecurity risks included). Such internal document of the Valkyries project was presented as Annex C in document D5.4 VALKYRIES harmonisations on first aid response common practices and procedures.

6. Harmonisations verified

6.1. Introduction

This chapter includes the template of VALKYRIES harmonisations that have been verified and validated, as reported in D7.3 System Validation and Evaluation.

The general template used for the harmonisations testing was the following:

Description: <>

Considerations: <>

Verification Method: <Inspection/Analysis/Test/Demo>

Type: <Functional/ Non-functional>

Traceability with identified requirements: <>

Traceability with VALKYRIES objectives:<>

Priority: <P1/P2/P3>

Associated test:

Test ID:	HO-5-X-Title
Level	Harmonization Opportunity 1
Type	<i>E.g., T3 – Functional tests</i>
Qualification method	<i>E.g., Analysis(A)</i>
Special Requirements	<i>E.g., N/A</i>
Information to collect	<i>E.g., Interfaces, data models, limitations of the technological deployment environment.</i>
Preprocessing/Analysis	<i>E.g., Execution of the functionality on the demonstrator and inspection of the result.</i>
Premises and limitations	<i>E.g., Limitations related to the capabilities of the virtualization platform on which the demonstrator is deployed.</i>
Security and Privacy Considerations	<i>E.g., It is assumed that the infrastructure involved complies with the relevant security and privacy policies. The resulting reports and information will be treated according to the contractually predefined levels of access and dissemination restrictions.</i>
Brief Description of the Test	<i>E.g., On the deployed demonstrator, test the possibility of configuration and networks. Check the result on the virtualized scenario. The result will be a calculation of the percentage of possible flexibility in configuration. In a complementary way, the number of resources consumed during the execution of the test battery will be tested, as well as its execution time.</i>

Table 2 – Associated test template

Criteria for assessing compliance:

HO-5-X-Title	Harmonisation description:
	<p>EM: Measures of mission success from the point of view of stakeholders.</p> <p>MR: Used to determine whether the system meets the performance harmonization opportunities needed to meet the EMs. E.g., Execution time (ms); resource consumption (memory, CPU.)</p> <p>KPI: Defined by stakeholders as measures of the minimum and critical performance of the system or process, as well as its level of acceptance. E.g., Adequacy (%). Penalties in execution time (ms) and resource consumption (%).</p> <p>Validation: Inspection/Analysis/Test/Demo, with the following valuation spectrum:</p> <p>A: Successful verification. Excellent results were observed (the best possible performance was observed). E.g., No cost in execution time or resources.</p> <p>B: Successful verification. Outstanding results (very good performance) were observed. E.g., High adequacy (90%). Small cost in execution time or resources.</p> <p>C: Successful verification. The results are in line with expectations. Average approval. E.g., High adequacy (70%). Resource cost less than 50%.</p> <p>D: Successful verification. There is a wide range of improvements to be considered in future work. Conditionally approved. Minimum degree of approval. E.g., Sufficient adequacy (>50%). Possible penalties in execution time and resources.</p> <p>E: Failed verification. The minimum verification conditions have not been exceeded E.g., Insufficient adequacy (<50%). Possible penalties in execution time and resources.</p>

Table 3 – Criteria for assessing compliance template

Results sheet:

Harmonisation Opportunity #ID to verify			
Description	Scope and coverage of the harmonisation opportunity (HO)		
Traceability	Traceability of the HO with respect to the tests carried out		
ME	MR	KPI	Verification method

Harmonisation Opportunity #ID to verify			
<i>Error rate (%), etc.</i>	<i>Milliseconds, CPU usage (%)</i>	<i>False positives, accuracy, variability, etc...</i>	<i>Inspection, analysis, etc.</i>
Verification action #1	Description	<i>Description of the action and its context. It includes premises, expected results, etc.</i>	
	Execution	<i>Step-by-step description of how the verification test was run.</i>	
	Analysis and results	<i>Description of the procedure for collecting results, its analytical actions (if necessary) and the general results achieved.</i>	
	History of corrective measures	<i>If the verification initially failed, this cell describes the different corrective actions to fit expectations.</i>	
	Lessons learned	<i>It highlights the difficulties suffered, and any possible conclusions or lessons learned to be considered in the later stages of development.</i>	
	Quality	<i>Functional score of the verification action [A, B, C, D, E]. The legend of the score varies depending on the element to be validated, being declared for each test along with the quality thresholds to be considered.</i>	
	End-user feedback	<i>Any comments highlighted by the end users of the Project during the verification process.</i>	
	Result	<i>YES/NO. Did you pass the test successfully? The achievement criteria require compliance with the verification (Quality Rating) and validation (Acceptance) criteria in accordance with the thresholds indicated.</i>	
Verification Action #2			
			...
verification action #n			

Table 4 – Results sheet template

Evidence of implementation and compliance:

As reported in D7.3.

6.2. Modules and federated systems verified against their interoperability

The SIGRUN system model consists of the modules as shown in the following system architecture diagram, where the operational services are external applications from End-Users; the Valkyries Interoperability Framework Services contain the modules and functions required to operate the system ; and the VIF CORE Services hold the critical and core modules requires to synchronize and execute the system. The connector holds the interfaces between the operational (Applications) services and the SIGRUN Framework and Core services, such as the SIGRUN API.

Figure 11 – Sigrun architecture diagram from D2.8

Such system is used to attach federated (trusted and tested) systems exchanging information based on VALKYRIES Minimum Data Set Schema.

This federated systems include the modules specially designed to run Sigrun's core functions and the interoperability framework, as well as the operational applications, such as:

- iSafety platform (Command and Control)
- Sigrun engine, Sigrun API platform, GLOBAL COP
- An application for digitalizing triage process
- TASSICA TB triage bracelets
- TAP2SOS system
- HTL platform

6.3. Integration and harmonization test results

The incremental testing of Sigrun modules versus relevant opportunities to harmonization results, as classified and valued during the Valkyries project, were designed to follow the steps before and during Use Cases (UC) execution/testing as in the table below:

OPPORTUNITY	USE CASE 1	USE CASE 2	USE CASE 3	USE CASE 4
CO.WP4.15: Location of near/nearest vehicles	X		X	X
CO.WP4.28: Cross border data trace		X	X	X
CO.WP4.42: Reduce voice communication, digitalising most information exchanges	X	X	X	X
CO.WP4.55: Use of wearable to support triage				X
CO.WP4.21: Historical data analysis from the missions and platforms	X	X	X	
CO.WP4.2: Logistics assistance using UAVs				X

OPPORTUNITY	USE CASE 1	USE CASE 2	USE CASE 3	USE CASE 4
CO.WP5-1: Standardization of terms in planning, preparedness and execution of the emergency response	X	X	X	X
CO.WP5-2: Harmonization of emergency response plans	X	X	X	
CO.WP5-3: Harmonization of alert and warning procedures in emergency response	X	X	X	
CO.WP5-7: Harmonization of operating procedures in emergency response	X	X	X	
CO.WP5-12: Standardization of information sharing in emergency response	X	X	X	
CO.WP5-13: Establishing a common federated system for sharing information in emergency response	X	X	X	
CO.WP6.2: Use of cryptographic mechanisms to protect data	X	X	X	
CO.WP6.11: Minimum set of competencies and skills for volunteers and integration in the field operational procedures.			X	
CO.WP6.7: Use of Virtual Operation Support Teams (VOSTs)		X		
CO.WP6.5: Standardization of education and training for first aid responses (Creation of a Training kit: curriculum, methodology and training manual).			X	
CO.WP6.10: Using common procedures and standards for training and civil-military actions			X	

Table 5 – Opportunities to be demonstrated in UCs

6.4. Integration test results

6.4.1. Integration Plan

The goal to check on a simple plan of the foreseen integration activities as consistent, logical, containing no gaps was achieved during the 4th plenary meeting of the Valkyries Consortium in Athens.

This planning resulted to:

- The validation of expectation/goals to be checked as in the Table 5 of the present document
- A path for an incremental integration testing of SIGRUN modules following the “sandwich” methodology

As this document reflects the result of this goal, this can be considered as achieved 100%.

6.4.2. SIGRUN components output format

Detailed testing of the accordance of the outputs of the different SIGRUN components which comply with the relevant standards, giving countable results in KPIs form has been executed through the SIGRUN module testing and harmonization performance reported in T7.4.

It must be noted that all critical SIGRUN components and modules were tested with success before and during **UCs**.

It must be noted that the blockchain logging module of SIGRUN was tested and verified/evaluated in UC3, even though it was ready for testing in UC1 also. As incremental sandwich methodology needed to test other modules or functions in UC1, the results for this module were concluded in UC3 only.

The following SIGRUN modules were successfully tested and verified:

Module/Function	Tested and verified in UC#	Application	Level of testing success
Core Services-SIGRUN TIME	3	BC2050 through Blockchain login module	Pass/Successful
Core Services-SSO and User Registration	1 and 3	iSafety	Pass/Successful
Core Services-Message Broker	1, 2, 3 and 4	SIGRUN API platform	Pass/Successful
Core Services-Registration Application	1, 2, 3 and 4	iSafety and SIGRUN API	Pass/Successful
Core Services-Blockchain Security	3	Blockchain developed module	Pass/Successful
Core Services-Data logger	3	Blockchain developed module	Pass/ Successful
Operational services- Situational awareness	1, 2, 3 and 4	iSafety , GLOBAL COP, SIGRUN API	Pass/ Successful
Operational services- C2 Planning and monitoring	1, 2, 3 and 4	iSafety , GLOBAL COP, SIGRUN API	Pass/ Successful
Operational services- COP	1, 2, 3 and 4	iSafety, GLOBAL COP and SIGRUN API	Pass/ Successful
Operational services- Digital TWIN (simulator)	1	HTL	Pass/ Successful
Medical Response-Victims' Registration	1, 2 and 3	Application for digitalizing triage process and TASSICA TB triage bracelets	Pass/ Successful
Medical Response-Victims' Location	3	TAP2SOS system and TASSICA TB triage bracelets	Pass/ Successful
Medical Response-Victims' Triage	1, 2 and 3	Application for digitalizing triage process	Pass/ Successful
Medical Response-Victims' Health Monitoring	1, 2 and 3	Application for digitalizing triage process	Pass/ Successful
Medical Response-Victims' Assigning and transportation	1, 2 and 3	Application for digitalizing triage process, iSafety, TASSICA TB triage bracelets and TAP2SOS system	Pass/ Successful
Medical Response-Hospital Response Capacity	1	iSafety , GLOBAL COP	Pass/ Successful

Module/Function	Tested and verified in UC#	Application	Level of testing success
Medical Response-Asset management and tracking	1, 2 and 3	iSafety , GLOBAL COP and application for digitalizing triage process	Pass/ Successful
Medical Response-Medical Information Exchange	1, 2 and 3	iSafety and application for digitalizing triage process	Pass/ Successful
Medical Response-Incident Management	1, 2 and 3	iSafety and application for digitalizing triage process	Pass/ Successful
Population Alert-Social Media		(Optional - Not used)	Not tested
Support- Login and Authentication	1, 2, 3 and 4	iSafety and all other federated applications	Pass/Successful
Support- Security Keys Management		(Optional - Not used)	Not tested
Support- Cross Border Info Management	1, 2, 3 and 4	iSafety, GLOBAL COP and SIGRUN API	Pass/partially Successful
Data Exchange-Status and availability	3	Blockchain logging module, SIGRUN API and SIGRUN Engine	Pass/Successful
Data Exchange-Data translation		(Optional - Not available)	Not tested
Data Exchange-Stream		(Optional - Not available)	Not tested
Data Exchange-Backup		(Optional - Not available)	Not tested
Data Exchange-Privacy Audit	1 and 3	iSafety and all other federated applications	Pass/Successful
Data Exchange- File Sharing	2, 3 and 4	iSafety, blockchain data logging and all other federated applications	Pass/Successful
Data Exchange-Multimedia communication	2	iSafety and all other federated applications	Pass/Successful
Communications resource management	1 and 3	iSafety	Pass/Successful

Table 6 – SIGRUN modules tested

It must be noted that the “Not tested” functionalities had passed previous integration tests and they could not be tested in UCs due to their design.

6.4.3. SIGRUN components input format

Detailed testing of the accordance of the inputs of the different SIGRUN components which comply with the relevant standards, giving countable results in KPIs form were tested, based on

- The minimum data set schemas for data exchanges
- The functionality of SIGRUN modules and components

The test results were, so far, similar with the ones presented in the Table 6.

6.4.4. Seamless operation of SIGRUN

Detailed testing of the execution time and synchronization of the procedures of the different components of SIGRUN were found in between acceptable limits for the seamless operation of SIGRUN, giving countable results in KPIs form so far.

6.4.5. SIGRUN's Layered architecture

The level of accordance of the integrated system (SIGRUN) complies with the envisioned Layered architecture with no major discrepancies or changes observed so far as per the basic results of D2.8.

6.4.6. SIGRUN's Extensibility

The level of accordance of the integrated system (SIGRUN) which SHALL comply with the envisioned Extensibility, based on data traffic and system stress tests performed with a limited number of users in UCs. Further stress test testing is recommended in order to conclude to final successful results on this goal.

6.4.7. SIGRUN'S Expandability

The level of accordance of the integrated system (SIGRUN) complies with the envisioned Expandability, as there is no major limitation or any technological restrictions for more federated systems to be attached to its core services, assuming that

- Comply with the minimum data set schema
- Can be successfully tested through APIs with the SIGRUN platform

In any case, special precautions should be made when any such new system is attached on victims' coding/Id and on the privileges, they provide to their users/roles.

6.4.8. SIGRUN's Interoperability

The level of accordance of the integrated system (SIGRUN) complies with the envisioned Interoperability with other systems following the same standards.

6.4.9. SIGRUN's Multi-level scalability

The level of accordance of the integrated system (SIGRUN) complies with the envisioned multi-level scalability under the assumptions that no performance problems will pop up in future more stress testing.

6.4.10. SIGRUN's privacy & data protection

The level of accordance of the integrated system (SIGRUN) fully complies with the EU privacy and data protection standards (GDPR and other Data/Service Acts in force), as the blockchain technologies used for secure data logging were designed exactly for this purpose.

6.4.11. SIGRUN's cybersecurity framework

The level of robustness of SIGRUN in terms of (cyber)security against threats comply with the relevant EU standards like Cybersecurity Act etc. as long as the procedures designed are followed, including the periodical update of installed security systems as per the risk assessment re-evaluation and re-definition.

As far as all SIGRUN modules/federated systems Administrators were provided by the companies that developed the ones, it should be noted that a full Security and Risk assessment exercise must be performed before taking the SIGRUN platform in real action as a product or service.

6.4.12. Overall Reference Integration and harmonisation evaluation

The collection of all previous outcomes of the above activities of T7.3 towards the final evaluation of the integration leads to the above analysis results:

1. Following the integration tests and the SIGRUN demo/use in UCs, there is strong evidence that the SIGRUN platform performs as scheduled and designed.
2. The perception/acceptance of end users/responders and the Agencies involved in the UCs has to be further analysed, comparing the actual measurable outcomes of the SIGRUN system versus the results of the systems in use. This information will be part of the UC reports delivered at the end of the project.
3. The harmonization level reached so far is directly related with the Opportunities/goals described in table 5 achievement as in the following table:

OPPORTUNITY	USE CASE 1	USE CASE 2	USE CASE 3	USE CASE 4
CO.WP4.15: Location of near/nearest vehicles	SIMULATED	SIMULATED		
CO.WP4.28: Cross border data trace		SIMULATED	YES	
CO.WP4.42: Reduce voice communication, digitalising most information exchanges	YES	YES	YES	
CO.WP4.55: Use of wearable to support triage		YES	YES	YES
CO.WP4.21: Historical data analysis from the missions and platforms	YES	YES	YES	
CO.WP4.2: Logistics assistance using UAVs				YES
CO.WP5-1: Standardization of terms in planning, preparedness and execution of the emergency response	YES		YES	
CO.WP5-2: Harmonization of emergency response plans	YES		YES	
CO.WP5-3: Harmonization of alert and warning procedures in emergency response	PARTIALLY	YES	PARTIALLY	
CO.WP5-7: Harmonization of operating procedures in emergency response	YES		YES	
CO.WP5-12: Standardization of information sharing in emergency response	YES		YES	
CO.WP5-13: Establishing a common federated system for sharing information in emergency response	ACCEPTED	ACCEPTED	ACCEPTED	ACCEPTED
CO.WP6.2: Use of cryptographic mechanisms to protect data	YES	YES	YES	YES
CO.WP6.11: Minimum set of competencies and skills for volunteers and integration in the field operational procedures.			YES	
CO.WP6.7: Use of Virtual Operation Support Teams (VOSTs)		SIMULATED		
CO.WP6.5: Standardization of education and training for first aid responses (Creation of a Training kit: curriculum, methodology and training manual).			YES	
CO.WP6.10: Using common procedures and standards for training and civil-military actions			YES	

Table 7 – Harmonisation level achieved

6.5. TRL level of the SIGRUN system

As defined in literature, a system Technology Readiness Level (TRL) of any technological system can be classified according to the schema as bellow:

Figure 12 – TRL classification

The result of the Valkyries project, the SIGRUN system was:

1. Observed as per its basic principles in the early stages before the submission of the Valkyries proposal
2. The Technology concept was formulated in WP2, as results in D2.8 whilst its functionality and technologies embedded within its design were defined and accepted in WP3 and WP4
3. The experimental proof of concept of the developed prototype was concluded before the execution of the UCs testing of the system, following the above defined design of the integrated tests in simulated environments. Such testing performed modules versus federated systems tests using test data as defined as minimum data set in WP2.
4. The extension of tests using test data and simulators was concluded also before UC1 through components and integration tests performed in nabs.
5. The technology was validated and demonstrated mainly in UC1, UC3 and UC4 whilst the design of UC2 repeated and confirmed the observed results/KPIs in a simulated environment with no different results than the ones already observed when reaching TRL6 and TRL7.

Following the above analysis, the SIGRUN system has reached a **TRL6 to TRL7** level following the completion of testing in UCs.

6.6. Lessons learned

Lessons learned so far conclude to the following:

1. More time should be left for developments/integration testing prior to in vivo testing of the SIGRUN system in UCs.

2. UCs designs should focus more on SIGRUN evaluation than executing exercises as usual, without the vast support of technologies such as the SIGRUN system
3. The analysis of end users perception/acceptance of the SIGRUN system must not be derived only through first responder's questionnaires, as major SIGRUN functionalities are visible only to C2 operators. C2 operation testing with trained professional's representatives of Civil Protection Agencies must be redesigned before the remaining UCs testing.

6.7. Recommendations for future testing and developments

For the limited time left until the completion of the Valkyries project, the following actions are recommended in order to achieve the best results possible towards VALKYRIES objectives:

1. For any future testing on developments, it will be crucial to define, in cooperation with the task leaders. UC leaders which topics or modules of SINGRUN will be tested during any new UC execution.
2. Such rescheduling has to include well defined actions during the UC execution that are not directly related with the first responders' view, perspective or expectations. These include:
 - a. A closer monitoring on COPs the relevant decision making taken using the SIGRUN versus the decision making taken in Command and Control Centres without the support of the SIGRUN system.
 - b. The use of internal procedures of the SIGRUN central operations against the major functionalities and workflows described in internal document added as Annex C in submitted document D5.4 VALKYRIES harmonisations on First aid response common practices and procedures.
 - c. If possible, the test versus more realistic simulations or scenarios where the most of the federated apps or systems have been registered and assigned to specific first responder Agencies.
3. Follow-up and wrap-up after the UCs multi victims cross border incidents must use, as much as possible, logged data in blockchain data base in order to derive with precise conclusions effecting KPI or other measurable performance indicators.

7. ANNEX A - Incremental test summary reports on SIGRUN modules

7.1. UC1 Integration test results

Before the UC1 execution, the following SIGRUN modules and federated applications attached were tested in two stages:

- Stage 1: Connectivity
- Stage 2: Interoperability

Systems in integration testing:

- iSafety platform
- SIGRUN engine, SIGRUN API platform, GLOBAL COP
- HTL platform
- An application for digitalizing triage process
- TASSICA TB triage bracelets

Figure 13 – GLOBAL COP general view

Figure 14 – GLOBAL COP Victims view

During stage 1, all systems were connected on an intranet, simulating the communication protocols defined in D2.8.

Figure 15 – GLOBAL COP staff and assets view

Having secured their connectivity in SIGRUN, simulated data created by iSafety and HTL were created for all organizations, resources and the MC Incidents created by the iSafety. No conflicts were reported.

Label	Last Updated	Gender	Age / Age Group	Assistance Status	AT	ET	Main Pathology	Transport	Destination	Location	Triage History	Incident	By Unit	By Staff
bd0c86c-ae35-45d7-b5e0-70c53941e620 [p jgff]	June 8, 2021, 10:18 a.m. 2 weeks, 1 day ago	♀	- / -							→	→	File		
5c7f68ff-027d-43d4-95e8-aa40dbd3f992 [i u]	June 8, 2021, 10:18 a.m. 2 weeks, 1 day ago	♂	- / -							→	→	File		
c150c3c6-7e03-4e10-ae40-b4253ed88825 [xx zzzzz]	June 8, 2021, 10:11 a.m. 2 weeks, 1 day ago	♂	- / -							→	→	File		
28d9aed7-d8e7-47a8-0242-512818650580 []	June 8, 2021, 8:24 a.m. 2 weeks, 4 days ago	♀	- / -							→	→	File		
d862c1a7-4c6a-4c47-a7a4-904d7130c69f [gg mh]	June 8, 2021, 8:23 a.m. 2 weeks, 4 days ago	♂	- / -							→	→	File		
a1ac52bf-d8d9-88d4-9b46-ac5b7c23f5f9 [gg mh]	June 8, 2021, 8:21 a.m. 2 weeks, 4 days ago	♂	- / -							→	→	File		
1df126be-0332-436d-b337-80c8039c773b	June 8, 2021, 8:19 a.m. 2 weeks, 4 days ago	♂	- / -							→	→	File		

Figure 16 – GLOBAL COP victims list

Following the UC landscape setup, multiple simulated victims were created using an application for digitalising the triage process and tracked either with this triage application or with the Global COP. No conflicts or duplications were reported.

Following the above predefined integration test, the attached systems were verified as able to be used in UC1.

7.2. UC3, UC2 and UC4 Integration test results

Following the successful repeat of the tests performed before UC1, the following SIGRUN modules and federated applications attached were tested in two stages for the next two UCs (UC3 and UC2):

- Stage 1: Connectivity
- Stage 2: Interoperability

Systems in integration testing:

- iSafety platform
- SIGRUN API and GLOBAL COP
- An application for digitalizing triage process
- Blockchain module of SIGRUN
- TAP2SOS as an alternative victims’ track and trace systems, supported by wearables
- TASSICA TB triage bracelets

TAP2SOS was tested in advance and victims created/registered by this application appeared smoothly on the GLOBAL COP and dashboards with no conflicts with victims created or their position generated by other applications. It was not possible to test this application during the execution of the UC2 and UC3 but it was presented and tested in the training session of the U3C by several first responders.

The blockchain module of SIGRUN developed by BC2050, had been tested stand alone as per its functionality, logging encrypted data on a private Blockchain network following the Ethereum standards. Such tests were performed using third party tools such as:

- **Geth:** set up and test the Ethereum client
- **Node.js, npm:** runtime environment and package manager
- **Truffle Suite:** deploy and test smart contracts
- **Web3.js:** interact with Ethereum nodes
- **Git:** version control
- **Remix:** deploy and debug smart contracts

The private blockchain network was deployed using Raspberry Pis running all needed Ethereum protocols and algorithms.

Figure 17 – Raspberry Pi module

Following this test, the module was attached in SIGRUN using PARTICLE’s API

```
Contract: VPPAuction
Contract Deployment
Contract Address: 0xE6a8CE2d1Ccd1c32be4b7EF6c3e1b3195A11495b
  ✓ Should Deploy Successfully
Auction Creation
  ✓ Should create a new auction (915ms)
Placing Bids
  ✓ Should place a valid bid (673ms)
  ✓ Should reject a lower bid (178ms)
  ✓ Should accept a higher bid (648ms)
  ✓ Should reject a bid with the same amount as the highest bid (122ms)
  ✓ Should reject a bid from the auction's seller (105ms)
  ✓ Should reject bid after auction end time and refund bidder1 (15112ms)
Seller calls endAuction after time passed:
  ✓ Should end the auction and transfer the highest bid to the seller (2382ms)
  ✓ Should reject ending the auction twice (133ms)
Events Emitted
  ✓ Should emit AuctionStarted event when auction is created (1114ms)
  ✓ Should emit HighestBidIncreased event when a valid bid is placed (628ms)
  ✓ Should emit AuctionEnded event when the auction is ended (7082ms)
Edge Cases
  ✓ Should accept a very high bid (715ms)
  ✓ Should reject a very low bid (103ms)
  ✓ Should reject a bid placed at the exact same time as the auction's end time (5117ms)
Multiple Sellers and Buyers
  ✓ Should allow multiple sellers to create auctions (386ms)
  ✓ Should allow multiple buyers to place bids on different auctions (1687ms)
Simultaneous Auctions with Different End Times
  ✓ Should allow bids on both auctions while they are active (2045ms)
  ✓ Should reject bids on the first auction after it ends, while the second auction is still active (10944ms)
  ✓ Should reject bids on both auctions after they have ended (10250ms)
  ✓ Should allow ending both auctions separately after their respective end times (7429ms)
Contract: VPPLogging
  ✓ should record energy transaction that also acts as a certificate (838ms)
  ✓ should fetch EnergyTransaction by the initial issuer (2498ms)
  ✓ should revert if non-owner tries to fetch energy transaction (1606ms)
  ✓ should return energy transactions by owner (1578ms)
  ✓ should return all energy transactions (2833ms)
27 passing (1m)
```

Figure 18 – Screenshot module deployment

Transactions and data/metadata exchanged through SIGRUN were logged smoothly with no loss of information or duplicates, causing no significant load to the systems employed for the integration test.


```
root@node1:~/blocktop_#./node1/node1/txns
09-20-2011:57:53.004 Commit new sealing work number=139,258 sealhash=311588...376390 uncles=0 txid=0 peer=
09-20-2011:57:55.959 Successfully sealed new block number=139,255 sealhash=021842...f4f0cc hash=86c231...4c4547 v1app=0.338s
09-20-2011:57:55.972 "mixed potential block" number=139,255 sealhash=06c523...4c4547
09-20-2011:58:01.211 Snapshot extension registration failed peer=dcac0a8... peer connected on snap without compatible eth support"
09-20-2011:58:02.803 Looking for peers peer=dcac0a8... peer connected on snap without compatible eth support"
09-20-2011:58:02.743 Successfully sealed new block number=139,258 sealhash=311588...376390 uncles=0 txid=0 peer=
09-20-2011:58:02.744 "block reached canonical chain" number=139,258 sealhash=02c4c0...388899
09-20-2011:58:02.745 "mixed potential block" number=139,258 sealhash=f0cc...f49915
09-20-2011:58:02.745 Commit new sealing work number=139,257 sealhash=336848...f10f92 uncles=0 txid=0 peer=
09-20-2011:58:02.746 Commit new sealing work number=139,257 sealhash=336848...f10f92 uncles=0 txid=0 peer=
09-20-2011:58:03.497 "block reached canonical chain" number=139,257 sealhash=336848...f10f92 uncles=0 txid=0 peer=
09-20-2011:58:03.498 "mixed potential block" number=139,258 sealhash=01179f...426036
09-20-2011:58:03.498 "mixed potential block" number=139,247 sealhash=02126e...33a113
09-20-2011:58:03.499 Commit new sealing work number=139,258 sealhash=02126e...33a113 uncles=0 txid=0 peer=
09-20-2011:58:03.499 Commit new sealing work number=139,258 sealhash=02126e...33a113 uncles=0 txid=0 peer=
09-20-2011:58:05.158 Snapshot extension registration failed peer=4b1c4e7... peer connected on snap without compatible eth support"
09-20-2011:58:07.768 Successfully sealed new block number=139,258 sealhash=367e2...0e0006 hash=f8e432...b3e44 v1app=0.269s
09-20-2011:58:07.769 "block reached canonical chain" number=139,258 sealhash=00217...248236
09-20-2011:58:07.769 "mixed potential block" number=139,248 sealhash=30a43e...33f44
09-20-2011:58:07.771 Commit new sealing work number=139,258 sealhash=3713a8...1f1024 uncles=0 txid=0 peer=
09-20-2011:58:07.772 Commit new sealing work number=139,258 sealhash=3713a8...1f1024 uncles=0 txid=0 peer=
09-20-2011:58:11.064 Successfully sealed new block number=139,259 sealhash=3713a8...1f1024 hash=f8669...573ac v1app=0.531s
09-20-2011:58:11.307 "block reached canonical chain" number=139,242 sealhash=023...c0d4f7
09-20-2011:58:11.312 Commit new sealing work number=139,258 sealhash=11892...81100 uncles=0 txid=0 peer=
09-20-2011:58:11.314 Commit new sealing work number=139,258 sealhash=11892...81100 uncles=0 txid=0 peer=
09-20-2011:58:11.314 "mixed potential block" number=139,249 sealhash=f8069...573ac
09-20-2011:58:17.183 Successfully sealed new block number=139,262 sealhash=271802...043306 hash=f6672...11037 v1app=0.866s
09-20-2011:58:17.184 "block reached canonical chain" number=139,263 sealhash=363765...5cc009
09-20-2011:58:17.194 "mixed potential block" number=139,266 sealhash=f16372...109577
09-20-2011:58:27.281 Commit new sealing work number=139,262 sealhash=040f7...066436 uncles=0 txid=0 peer=
09-20-2011:58:27.282 Commit new sealing work number=139,262 sealhash=040f7...066436 uncles=0 txid=0 peer=
09-20-2011:58:27.282 Looking for peers peer=113...113
09-20-2011:58:24.192 Successfully sealed new block number=139,262 sealhash=104f7...066436 hash=8c08c...a33f2 v1app=0.944s
09-20-2011:58:24.193 "block reached canonical chain" number=139,264 sealhash=3374...04838
09-20-2011:58:24.193 "mixed potential block" number=139,261 sealhash=9c08c...a33f2
09-20-2011:58:24.195 Commit new sealing work number=139,262 sealhash=28381...f730a8 uncles=0 txid=0 peer=
09-20-2011:58:24.195 Commit new sealing work number=139,262 sealhash=28381...f730a8 uncles=0 txid=0 peer=
09-20-2011:58:25.914 Successfully sealed new block number=139,262 sealhash=108161...f730a8 hash=4337e...9e4e22 v1app=0.113s
09-20-2011:58:25.915 "block reached canonical chain" number=139,263 sealhash=06c523...4c4547
09-20-2011:58:25.915 "mixed potential block" number=139,262 sealhash=04357e...9b0227
09-20-2011:58:25.915 Commit new sealing work number=139,263 sealhash=18c139...0777a uncles=0 txid=0 peer=
09-20-2011:58:25.916 Commit new sealing work number=139,263 sealhash=18c139...0777a uncles=0 txid=0 peer=
09-20-2011:58:32.218 Looking for peers peer=113...113
09-20-2011:58:42.364 Looking for peers peer=113...113
09-20-2011:58:46.857 Successfully sealed new block number=139,263 sealhash=18c139...0777a hash=f6cf7...104069 v1app=0.141s
09-20-2011:58:46.938 "block reached canonical chain" number=139,246 sealhash=f96c...f49915
09-20-2011:58:46.938 "mixed potential block" number=139,263 sealhash=f6cf7...104069
09-20-2011:58:46.961 Commit new sealing work number=139,264 sealhash=eadf83...1160f0 uncles=0 txid=0 peer=
09-20-2011:58:46.961 Commit new sealing work number=139,264 sealhash=eadf83...1160f0 uncles=0 txid=0 peer=
09-20-2011:58:46.962 Commit new sealing work number=139,264 sealhash=eadf83...1160f0 uncles=0 txid=0 peer=
09-20-2011:58:46.962 Looking for peers peer=113...113
09-20-2011:58:46.962 "block reached canonical chain" number=139,267 sealhash=eadf83...1160f0 hash=31649...39e4fc v1app=0.1391s
09-20-2011:58:46.962 "mixed potential block" number=139,267 sealhash=02126e...33a113
09-20-2011:58:46.957 Commit new sealing work number=139,264 sealhash=eadf83...1160f0 uncles=0 txid=0 peer=
09-20-2011:58:46.957 Commit new sealing work number=139,265 sealhash=02126e...33a113 uncles=0 txid=0 peer=
09-20-2011:58:46.957 Looking for peers peer=113...113
09-20-2011:58:46.957 "block reached canonical chain" number=139,268 sealhash=30a43e...33f44
09-20-2011:58:46.972 "mixed potential block" number=139,265 sealhash=02126e...33a113
09-20-2011:58:46.972 Commit new sealing work number=139,268 sealhash=02126e...33a113 uncles=0 txid=0 peer=
09-20-2011:58:46.972 Commit new sealing work number=139,268 sealhash=02126e...33a113 uncles=0 txid=0 peer=
09-20-2011:58:47.479 Looking for peers peer=113...113
09-20-2011:58:47.479 Successfully sealed new block number=139,268 sealhash=30a43e...33f44 hash=82701...17b3f2 v1app=0.012s
09-20-2011:58:47.479 "block reached canonical chain" number=139,265 sealhash=02126e...33a113
09-20-2011:58:47.479 Commit new sealing work number=139,268 sealhash=02126e...33a113 uncles=0 txid=0 peer=
09-20-2011:58:47.481 Commit new sealing work number=139,268 sealhash=02126e...33a113 uncles=0 txid=0 peer=
09-20-2011:58:47.481 Successfully sealed new block number=139,268 sealhash=02126e...33a113 hash=0520e...129b44 v1app=0.2.699s
09-20-2011:58:48.182 "block reached canonical chain" number=139,249 sealhash=f8069...573ac
09-20-2011:58:48.209 Commit new sealing work number=139,267 sealhash=eadf83...1160f0 uncles=0 txid=0 peer=
09-20-2011:58:48.211 Commit new sealing work number=139,267 sealhash=eadf83...1160f0 uncles=0 txid=0 peer=
09-20-2011:58:48.211 "mixed potential block" number=139,266 sealhash=06c523...4c4547
09-20-2011:58:48.426 Looking for peers peer=113...113
09-20-2011:58:48.464 "block reached canonical chain" number=139,268 sealhash=f16372...109577
09-20-2011:58:48.464 Commit new sealing work number=139,268 sealhash=f16372...109577 uncles=0 txid=0 peer=
09-20-2011:58:48.464 Commit new sealing work number=139,268 sealhash=f16372...109577 uncles=0 txid=0 peer=
09-20-2011:58:48.464 Successfully sealed new block number=139,267 sealhash=eadf83...1160f0 hash=82701...17b3f2 v1app=0.2.278s
09-20-2011:58:48.487 "mixed potential block" number=139,267 sealhash=04357e...9b0227
09-20-2011:58:49.716 Snapshot extension registration failed peer=0ca2988... peer connected on snap without compatible eth support"
09-20-2011:58:49.809 Looking for peers peer=113...113
```

Figure 19 – Transactions log

8. ANNEX B – References

- REF. 1 D2.1: Definition of System Requirements and Demonstration Use Cases
- REF. 2 D2.2: Terminology and Semantics
- REF. 3 D2.5: Harmonisation framework
- REF. 4 D6.1: Landscape of emerging preparedness and cross-sectorial collaboration opportunities for first aid response on multi-casualty disasters
- REF. 5 D5.1: Landscape of emerging operational and procedural opportunities for first aid response on multi-casualty disasters
- REF. 6 D5.4 VALKYRIES harmonisations on first aid response common practices and procedures
- REF. 7 D4.1: Landscape of emerging technological opportunities for first aid response on multi-casualty disasters
- REF. 8 VALKYRIES D5.2
- REF. 9 D3.3: Roadmap for enhancing the pan- European technological capabilities for first aid response on multi-casualty disasters
- REF. 10 D2.8 Architecture Design Document
- REF. 11 D7.8 Report on the use case: Norway-Sweden-Denmark
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9. ANNEX C - Glossary

Acronym	Description
COP	Common Operational Picture
CPU	Central Processing Unit
EM	Effectiveness measures
EMS	Emergency Medical Services
EU	European Union
EUR-ERP	EU Emergency Response Plans
FR	First Responder
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation
GPS	Global Positioning System
Health ITUES	Health Information Technology Usability and Usefulness Evaluation Scale
HO	Harmonisation Opportunity
HTL	Hybrid Twin Lab
HTTPS	HyperText Transfer Protocol Secure
ID	Identification
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
MCI	Multi-Casualty Incident
METHANE	Acronym of <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Major Incident Declared • Exact location • Type of incident • Hazards • Access • Number and type of casualties • Emergency services present and required Report Methodology report for alerting others about a major incident
MR	Performance Measures
N/A	Not Applicable
ToC	Table of Content
TBD	To Be Defined
TBR	To Be Reviewed
UC	Use Case
VMI	Virtual Machine Interface

Table 8 – Glossary

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